

Spectrum, aetiology and clinical features of intracranial hypertension presenting in THQ Hospital, Muridky, Sheikhpura

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To assess spectrum, clinical features and etiologies of patients of intracranial hypertension.

Study Design: Cross-sectional study.

Place and duration of study: In THQ Hospital, Muridky, Sheikhpura from January, 2017 to July, 2018.

Patients and Methods: A total of 67 individuals with Intracranial Hypertension (IH) were screened on the basis of selection criteria resulting in 32 patients for final analysis. The demographics, clinical features and etiologies were recorded for each patient and presented through frequencies and percentages.

Results: On the basis of demographics, females (n = 26; 81.25 %) with age range of 20 to 30 (n = 12; 37.5 %) and obesity (n = 3; 9.3 %) showed high prevalence. Among clinical features, head ache (n = 22; 68.75 %) was most prominent. On the other hand, idiopathic intracranial pressure (43.7 %) showed highest prevalence.

Conclusion: High prevalence of IH in females with age 20 to 30, obesity and pregnancy indicates high susceptibility of this population.

Keywords: aetiology, hypertension, intracranial hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

Intracranial hypertension (IH) refers to building up of pressure around brain. It mainly comprises of neurological disorders in which cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) pressure is increased within the skull. Although pressure of CSF varies in accordance with age, there is a certain limit for each age range. The pressure of CSF above 200 mm H₂O in children and above 25 mm H₂O in adults indicates increased intracranial pressure (ICP)(1).

The IH can occur due to brain abscess, stroke or severe head injury, resulting in acute IH. On the other hand, continuous presence of IH can result in chronic form. However, chronic IH is a rare problem. The IH usually result from a neurological injury or insult. Anyhow, sometimes IH may occur due to an unknown cause, known as idiopathic IH(2).

The etiology of intracranial hypertension is mainly divided into two categories including primary or

intracranial causes and secondary or extracranial causes. The intracranial causes include stroke, brain tumor, meningitis, hydrocephalus, non-traumatic intracerebral hemorrhage, trauma, or idiopathic IH. The secondary reasons comprises of hypertension, seizures, high altitude cerebral edema, hypoventilation, hyperpyrexia, metabolic disorder, and airway obstruction (3). On the basis of etiology of IH, the epidemiology may vary. The most prevalent type of IH is idiopathic IH, which mainly affects pregnant women. Other important risk factors for IH include obesity, chronic hypertension, history of medications, and comorbidity (4).

A variety of clinical features are associated with IH including nausea, vomiting, headache, altered consciousness level, ocular palsies, papilledema and back pain. If remained unchecked, papilledema can result in optic atrophy, visual disturbance and blindness (5). Further symptoms include abducens palsies, pupillary dilatation and Cushing's triad. The features of widened pulse pressure, elevated systolic blood pressure, abnormal respiratory pattern and bradycardia are associated with Cushing's triad (6).

The cerebral pressure, referring to pressure of blood flow in brain, is consistent in normal conditions due to autoregulation. An important outcome of IH is the occurrence of ischemia. The changes in cerebral pressure raise systemic blood pressure and dilation of cerebral blood vessels. The bleeding of intracranial hemorrhages and brain infarction may occur as a result (2).

The problem of IH can be life threatening. The annual incidence of IH was estimated to be 1 per 100,000 individuals (5). However, it has increased to 13 cases per 100,000 individuals, according to recent estimates (7). This abrupt increase in incidence of disease has mainly been attributed to obesity. The highest incidence of 21 cases per 100,000 individuals has been recorded in obese women with age range of 15 to 44 years (8). On the other hand, Ireland has the highest prevalence of 28 cases per 100,000 individuals, per year (1).

Despite the emerging prevalence of IH in various countries, Pakistan has lacked behind in exploring different aspects of the disease. Owing to the increasing obesity throughout the world, it is expected that IH will continue to increase in upcoming years. Thus, it has become important to understand various perspectives associated with IH. Thus, the present study aims to assess the etiologies and ophthalmological features of patients presenting in Neuro-ophthalmology OPD having raised intracranial pressure.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted to assess etiologies and clinical features of patients having complaint of intracranial hypertension (IH). For this purpose, a total of 67 patients referred to Neuro-ophthalmology OPD from January 2017 to July 2018 were included in the present study. These patients were referred from neurology OPD and other ophthalmology clinics. The consent forms were collected from willing participants, after explaining them purpose of the study and convincing about confidentiality of the data.

The detailed history, clinical examination, neuroimaging and laboratory data of patients were assessed and analyzed. The inclusion criteria comprised of individuals with headache and optic disc swelling. The patients with incomplete data were excluded. Individuals with issue of secondary IH and papilloedema secondary to space occupying lesion of brain were also not included in the study. The demographics of patients were noted, including age, gender and body mass index (BMI). The patients within age range of 10 to 60 years were included. Record of patient names, primary diagnosis, secondary diagnosis, procedures, and date of admission was also collected. The inclusion

criteria was based on Modified Dandy Criteria, which comprises of papiloedema, normal MRI, Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis and intracranial pressure of 25 cm H₂O on lumbar puncture or CSF infusion study. Apart from this, visual field charting, CT scan, MRI brain, MR venography were performed for all the patients. Laboratory tests included hematological analysis comprising of RBS, urea, and FBS. Serological analysis constituting of HCV and HBV was also performed for each case. Only 32 patients fulfilled the selection criteria, and were selected for final analysis.

The clinical features such as headache, tinnitus, diplopia, and transient visual obscurations, were recorded. Moreover, possible etiologies were noted for each patient. This included hydrocephalus, brain tumors, trauma, non-traumatic intracerebral hemorrhage, and idiopathic intracranial hypertension.

The data is analyzed by software SPSS. The variables are presented with the help of frequencies and standard deviations. The variables of age and BMI are depicted through means and standard deviations.

RESULTS

The demographic data of participants is shown in Table 1. The mean age of participants was 21.5 ± 3.4 years, lying between 13 years to 56 years. Majority of the participants had age range of 21 to 30 years. On the basis of gender distribution, high prevalence was noted among females (n = 26; 81.25 %) as compared to males (n = 6; 18.75 %). Majority of the patients had BMI lying in range of overweight (n = 15; 46.8 %). However, only 3 (9.3 %) patients had reported obesity on the basis of BMI. The mean BMI was 30.7 ± 2.5 kg/m².

Table 1: Demographics

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
10-20	4	12.5
21-30	12	37.5
31-40	9	28.1
41-50	5	15.6
51-60	2	6.2
Gender		
Male	6	18.75
Female	26	81.25
BMI (kg/m²)		
Underweight	1	3.1
Normal	13	40.6
Overweight	15	46.8
Obese	3	9.3

The Table 2 depicts clinical features of patients. In total, 22 (68.75 %) were reported with headache. Tinnitus was present in 4 (12.5 %), diplopia in 3 (9.3 %), and transient visual obscurations in 10 (31.25 %) patients. However, 1 (3.1 %) patient was asymptomatic. Mean intracranial pressure was 32 cm H₂O.

Table 2: Clinical features

Clinical features	Frequencies (n)	Percentages (%)
Headache	22	68.75
Tinnitus	4	12.5
Diplopia	3	9.3
Transient visual obscurations	10	31.25
Asymptomatic	1	3.1

The signs observed for patients included severe visual (n = 3; 9.3 %), moderate visual loss (n = 2; 6.2 %), disc swelling (n = 32; 100 %), mild disc swelling (n = 5; 15.6 %), severe disc swelling (n = 19; 59.3), swelling with hges (n = 4; 12.5 %), optic atrophy unilateral (n = 3; 9.3 %), periphlebitis (n = 1; 3.1 %), and uveitis (n = 1; 3.1 %).

The risks for IH include systematic associations and use of medications. Systematic associations in some patients were reported with pregnancy (n = 1; 3.1 %), anemia (n = 11; 34.3 %), sleep apnea (n = 3; 9.3 %), and hypertension (n = 6; 18.7 %). Some of other important systematic associations found in patients included polycystic ovary disease (n = 1; 3.1 %), increased PTH level (n = 3; 9.3); parathyroid adenoma (n = 1; 3.1 %), hypothyroidism (n = 2; 6.25), celiac disease (n = 2; 6.25) and menstrual irregularities (n = 3; 9.3 %). Some of the patients were reported with history of medications. These medications included hormonal supplements in 6 (18.75 %), vitamin A in 2 (6.25 %) and steroids/deltacortil in 2 (6.25 %) patients. Only one case required surgical intervention.

The etiologies of participants have been shown in the Table 3. The most prominent etiology was idiopathic intracranial hypertension with 43.7 %. This was followed by brain tumor with prevalence of 15.6 %. All other etiologies including trauma, non-traumatic intracerebral hemorrhage and hydrocephalus had prevalence of 3.1 %.

Table 3: Etiologies

Etiologies	Frequencies (n)	Percentages (%)
Trauma	1	3.1
Brain tumor	5	15.6
Non-traumatic intracerebral hemorrhage	1	3.1
Idiopathic intracranial hypertension	14	43.7
Hydrocephalus	1	3.1

DISCUSSION

The findings of present study suggest that IH is more prominent among female population. It was observed to occur in 81.25 % females, whereas, males had prevalence of 18.75 % only. This observation is supported by previous works of Ma et al. (4), Alali et al. (9) and Mondragon & Klovenski (2). Many previous research works have emphasized that IH is highly associated with female gender. The most prominent risk factors in females are age range of 20 to 30, obesity and pregnancy(3). The present study is in accordance with these findings of previous researchers. In present study, highest prevalence was observed for age range of 20 to 30 (37.5 %). On the other hand, 3 (9.3 %) patients had obesity and 15 (46.8 %)

were reported to be overweight. Although 40.6 % and 3.1 % of patients had normal weight and underweight, other risk factors were prominent in these individuals. This is in accordance with the study of Haq et al (8), who found that IH occurs mostly in females with age range 20 to 44 years with weight above than the normal one.

Clinical features of patients had high variety. However, headache was observed in majority of cases (n = 22; 68.75 %). This indicates high association of headache with IH. This was followed by transient visual obscurations (31.25 %), tinnitus (12.5 %), and diplopia (9.3 %). Previous research work of Haq et al (8) has shown high association of headache (100 %) with IH, which supports findings of the present study.

Other important systematic associations included anemia and hypertension. The work of Ananth et al (11) has previously indicated linkage of IH with anemia, whereas, association of hypertension with IH has previously been highlighted by the work of Pai et al (3). Although pregnancy has overly been emphasized by previous research works of Stevens et al. (10) and Pal et al. (11), the present study reports pregnancy in only one individual (3.1 %).

Use of different medications can also be associated with IH. This has been advocated by research work of Tan et al (13). Similar findings were deduced from present research work. The patients had history of using various medications such as diltiazem, hydroxychloroquine, isotretinoin and steroids. However, the most eminent medications among patients were hormonal supplements.

Numerous research works, such as Sharma et al (14), Zanon et al (15), Mollan et al (16),

Lichtenberg et al (17) and Kilgore et al (18) have emphasized on high prevalence of idiopathic intracranial hypertension. The present study is in accordance with these research works as idiopathic intracranial hypertension accounted for 43.7 % of cases

CONCLUSION

The aggressive course of intracranial hypertension can result in blindness over a short period of time. Strong association of intracranial hypertension with severe headache can help in early diagnosis and treatment of the problem. This can help in hindering visual loss and other complications. High prevalence of IH in females with age 20 to 30, obesity and pregnancy indicates high susceptibility of this population. Thus, individuals showing relevant clinical features and risk factors should be considered for abrupt treatment in order to avoid adverse outcomes.

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